

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Supratman**FIRST NAME:** Evlyne**PROGRAM CODE:** LLM**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Word 2016 on Windows 10

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Structure (EUCLID 2019, 3)
2. Referencing the Essay (EUCLID 2019, 4)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5–12)
4. Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14–16)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24–26)

USING THE ACADEMIC WRITING PRINCIPLE AS A NAVIGATION TOWARDS OUTSTANDING LEARNING OUTCOME

1) INTRODUCTION

My job as a legal corporate requires me to travel a lot by car alone, and I tend to use GPS navigation to guide me towards my destination. In the case of taking the LLM degree program at EUCLID University, my final destination certainly is to acquire complete knowledge on International Law and Treaty Law as an outstanding learning outcome. I had always believed that academic papers, such as response paper, essay quiz, and thesis, are an effective way to measure student's understanding of the learning material that has been taught. Therefore, the quality of learning outcomes is highly correlated with the quality of the academic writing itself. Thus, to get to my final destination, I will use the academic writing principle as navigation to get there.

Just like a GPS navigation that has elements to show me directions, the academic writing principle also has guidelines. Therefore, the first step I should do is mastering these guidelines to be able to write a good and acceptable academic writing according to EUCLID's standard. Fortunately, the assigned study material for this period, ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 and the EUCLID Video on Academic Paper Writing provide me with

complete guidance from the basic to the essential requirements of academic writing. Along with the start of the ACA-401 course, here begins my journey following the navigation towards my final destination.

2) **ELEMENTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING PRINCIPLES**

Similar to GPS navigation, which typically has elements to inform directions, academic writing principles also have guiding elements too. Based on the ACA-401 coursepack period 1 and the learning material video, I am able to summarize key elements of good academic writing principles. The first element to pay attention to is the **structure** of the essay. We have to consider the structure since we started drafting the essay. Every essay should include the following structure, which starts from the introduction, then the body, and ends with a conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). Personally, I find these basic rules very related to the flow of logic in developing academic writing. By using a proper structure, it will make the essay more systematic so that every idea, argument, and evidence that supports it is easier to be understood.

The second element that needs to be taken seriously in academic writing is **plagiarism**. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5). I personally have a strong disagreement over all acts of plagiarism. In the ACA-401 coursepack period 1, it is mentioned that the act of plagiarism is very wrong and unethical; it is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit; and it is an academic offense with serious consequences (ibid.). I could not agree more about this statement, and so to avoid plagiarism, we have to give credit to the author or source that provides the information we are using by properly citing them (EUCLID 2019, 6). The coursepack and the assigned video mentioned 4 ways to **referencing the essay**, which is an in-text citation, footnote, endnote, and bibliography. According to the assigned video, EUCLID suggests using the in-text citation for a response paper. The format of references depends on what style guide and language that we choose. I found an interesting example of this in the assigned video. When we are quoting using the US language, the arrangement starts with a double quote, followed by the quote, a punctuation mark, a double quote, then ended with a reference number without space. On the other hand, when we are quoting using the UK language, the arrangement starts with a double quote, followed by the quote, a double quote, a punctuation mark, and ended with a reference number without space. Meanwhile, Latin abbreviations like *ibid* and *op.cit*, are often used in reference. Therefore, having a knowledge of common Latin abbreviations and expressions is necessary, not only for reference purposes but also because the English equivalent of the abbreviations is often used to avoid misinterpretation by the readers (EUCLID 2019, 57).

The third element of good academic writing is the main thesis. It is preferable to be stated at the beginning of the essay or at least near it (EUCLID 2019, 14). By always stating it at the beginning of the essay, it will help me to stay focus on answering the question or the theories that are being discussed. Stating the main thesis is essential as it is the **first rule of thumb for writing papers** that are mentioned on the coursepack. However, there

are also other rules of thumb in the coursepack that are not less important, such as (EUCLID 2019, 14–16):

- Avoid lead with, or conclude with, or otherwise include sweeping generalities
- Write clearly
- Avoid making the writing boring and clumsy
- Support assertions
- Take the views of what been discuss seriously
- Avoid plagiarize

I find all these rules of thumb are applicable while I am writing this first response paper. Although, I also find a bit of difficulty with avoiding lead with sweeping generalities because it is a new thing that I learn since all my previous education did not teach me this, and I notice that I tend to do this as a habit.

The last element is a **style guide**. A Style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2019, 24). EUCLID recommends its student to use the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as a style guide (ibid.). Therefore, we should adhere to the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet (EUCLID 2019, 44). The crib sheet contains specific instructions on how to use the Chicago style, such as usage of capitalization, usage of a compound word, proper page format, etc. (EUCLID 2019, 44–55). I spend the most time reading the coursepack in this chapter, considering a style guide is also a new thing for me to learn, and it has a lot of detailed information. To be honest, I found this chapter challenging because it encourages me to develop my accuracy in checking my writing and my ability to memorize all the rules in the crib sheet in the shortest amount of time as possible. As a beginner learner of Chicago style, I think it might take a while for me to adapt and apply the Chicago style perfectly into my writing, nevertheless I fully understand that it is not an excuse for any mistake that might appear in my writing. However, I believe by practicing and learning continuously from every mistake that I make, I will eventually master the use of Chicago style.

3) CONCLUSION

The use of GPS navigation on my regular basis as a guide to my destination makes me see the requirements of writing good academic writing as something similar. Like a GPS navigation that has elements to determine the direction, academic writing principles certainly also have guiding elements that need to be followed to be able to achieve an outstanding learning outcome. I summarize the key points of the ACA-401 coursepack period 1 and the assigned video into 4 elements of the academic writing principle for my personal study material. The first element is the structure of the essay, which can significantly influence the systematic and logical flow of the essay, and it also related to effectively delivering the main ideas, arguments, and supporting evidence to the reader. The second element is plagiarism, which is an unethical act and can be considered as a serious academic offense. We have to avoid it by giving credit to the author or source that provides the information we are using by properly citing them in the references of the

essay. There are 4 ways to reference that mentioned in the coursepack and the assigned video, which for a response paper, EUCLID recommend using the in-text citation. The usage of Latin abbreviations also expected to be found in references. Therefore, having knowledge of Latin abbreviations and expression can become an advantage, for it also often appear in various writing. The third element is the main thesis, which needs to be stated, preferably at the beginning of the essay or at least near it (EUCLID 2019, 14). It is important to be done as well as other rules of thumb on the coursepack. Finally, the fourth element is a style guide, which EUCLID recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as a style guide. Fortunately, the coursepack provides us with the CMS crib sheet as it contains specific instructions on how to use the Chicago style properly. Undoubtedly, the crib sheet will be a frequently-used manual for a beginner learner like me, along with the coursepack as a whole. I believe that the elements of the academic writing principles are not just those mentioned above, yet there is more to learn with every period in the ACA-401 course, but one thing for sure is every element will guide me closer to my final destination.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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